

ZONE OF CROSSING “GOOD” AND “BAD” CONCEPTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10250617>

Annotation: This article emphasizes that the concepts of “good” and “evil” in philosophy are closely related to each other, and “good” and “evil” are moral concepts and are the main indicators of human morality. The intersection of the concepts of “good” and “evil” is analyzed using examples.

Key words: good, evil, good, evil, concept, intersection, area, properties, morality, essence, standard.

Ideas about good and evil have a significant impact on our daily lives and the lives of those around us. Good deeds create a positive atmosphere and strengthen our relationships with other people. Bad actions can have negative consequences and have a detrimental effect on our own lives.

Therefore, it is very important to pay attention to actions and strive for goodness in everyday life. Even a small act of kindness can make a big difference not only in our lives, but also in the lives of others.

Table comparing the concepts of “good” and “evil”

Characteristics	Kindness	Evil
Description	Positive actions, values and moral principles that promote human well-being and happiness	Negative actions, values, and moral principles that cause harm and suffering to people
Its role in ethics	“Good” is the basis of moral norms and values that help people live justly and happily	“Evil” is the opposite of good and refers to the violation of moral norms and values
Characteristics	“Kindness” has characteristics such as selflessness, compassion, justice and nobility	“Evil” is characterized by selfishness, cruelty, injustice and meanness
relativity	“Kindness” can be relative and influenced by cultural, social and	“Badness” can also be relative and vary depending on context and point of

	individual factors	view
In everyday life	“Goodness” is demonstrated by doing good deeds, helping others, respecting others, and following moral standards	“Evil” manifests itself in cruelty, violence, deception, crime, and violation of moral principles

The intersection of good and evil is an area where there are elements and actions that can be associated with both good and evil at the same time. It is here that the boundaries between concepts are “blurred” (mixed) and complex ethical problems arise.

For example, an example of an intersectional space would be a situation where a person takes an action that benefits one group of people, but at the same time harms another group. At the same time, depending on which side you look at, this move can be considered either good or bad.

Additionally, the field of intersectionality can include moral dilemmas where there is no clear answer about what is right and wrong. For example, euthanasia (Greek: the practice of causing a person or other living being to suffer an incurable disease and experience unbearable suffering as a result of this disease), the use of violence in self-defense.

Overall, the intersection of “good” and “bad” is a complex and multifaceted area where moral and sociocultural factors can influence our perception and evaluation of actions and events.

Below are examples of the intersection of the concepts of “good” and “evil”:

1. Help and suicide. The issues of euthanasia and suicide raise difficult ethical dilemmas. On the one hand, assisted dying can be seen as an act of compassion and relief of suffering. On the other hand, this can be considered a violation of the norms of life and morality.

2. War and defense. Military conflicts raise questions about when the use of force can be justified. For example, violence in self-defense can be considered a defensive act and therefore “good.” However, wars and acts of aggression can cause suffering and death and can therefore be considered "evil".

3. Cruelty and justice. The death penalty and cruel punishment are controversial. Some may believe that the death penalty provides fair punishment for serious crimes and public safety. However, others may consider

this a violation of human rights and cruelty. However, assessment and perception can be individual and depend on many factors.

4. Self-defense and violence. The question of when it is morally permissible to use violence in self-defense is controversial. For example, if someone is in danger and is threatened with physical violence, it may be considered “good” to use violence to protect oneself or others. However, even in such cases, questions arise about the proportionality and necessity of violence.

5. The desire for success and selfishness. How selfish behavior can be justified in the pursuit of personal success is also controversial. Some may view self-care and success as normal and positive. At the same time, others may view selfishness and disregard for the interests of other people as “evil.”

6. Lies and defense. Questions about when it is justified to lie to protect or benefit other people are also up for debate. For example, some may believe that it is okay to lie a little to keep a secret or to protect the feelings of others. However, others believe that lying is always “bad” and is a breach of trust.

The concepts of “good” and “bad” are the basic principles that shape human values and standards. In everyday use, the word "good" refers to things that are moral, just, and beneficial, while the word "bad" refers to things that are immoral or harmful. However, the line between good and evil is not always obvious. There are many situations and problems that are not easily classified as good or bad, and in this case they overlap.

For example, lying is usually considered bad, but lying to protect someone from injustice in this case may be considered a morally right thing to do. The intersection of good and evil is evident in these complex situations. These words overlap because the meanings of good and evil can be used in contrast to each other.

Traits such as honesty and loyalty are generally virtues, but when taken to extremes they can have detrimental consequences. Politeness and voluntary absolute honesty can sometimes harm people, and blind loyalty without moral restraint can lead to motivation for unethical actions. This shows that even good principles require thoughtful implementation. In fact, the lines between ethical and unethical are often blurred rather than clearly demarcated.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the concepts of “good” and “bad” are deeply and complexly interconnected. By philosophically analyzing the relationship between good and evil, we can try to expand the scope of justice and maximize welfare.

List of used literature:

1. Shchur G.S. Field theories in linguistics. – M.: 1974. – 256 p.

2. Nietzsche F.V. So spoke to Zarathustra. – Astrel, Harvest, 2013.
3. Nietzsche F.W. Genealogy of morality. Translator: V.A. Weinstock. – St. Petersburg, 2007.
4. Kierkegaard S. Fear and Trembling. Translator: Isaev S.A., Isaeva N.V. – Moscow, 2010.
5. Augustine A. Confession. – St. Petersburg, 2022.
6. Kant I. Fundamentals of the metaphysics of morality. – Moscow: Higher School, 1988.